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Respectfulness by Design (abstract)

The widespread trend of anthropomorphising technology, on the one hand, and the demand on fine-tuning social robots and “smart” devices to the emotional needs of human users,¹ on the other, create a need for artificial respectfulness the same way as they create the need for artificial trustworthiness and responsibility. There are two problems waiting for us here.

First, respect, like trust and responsibility, is an expectation that we have from the parties involved in *interpersonal relationships*, that is, relationships that, thus far, have been reserved for humans, such as friendship, companionship² (e.g. Wilks 2010), love and sexual relationship (e.g. Levy 2007, Danaher 2017), care and therapy (e.g. Wada & Shibata 2007; Turkle 2004; Turkle et al. 2006; Richardson et al. 2018), and pedagogical relationships (e.g. Kim 2005; Veletsianos & Miller 2008). Robots and AI are quickly being introduced and absorbed into these relationships. Normally, we expect those with whom we engage in these kinds of relationships to be trustworthy in some sense; we expect them to respect us; and we expect them to be responsible for their actions toward us. The problem with robotics and AI is that, as they enter these relationships, they become players in these relationships (playing the role of partner, caregiver, therapist, etc.), without being able to respond to these demands and expectations in the way humans can. This leads many to reflect on the way the introduction of computer technology, including robotics, is transforming our relationships with each other (see e.g. Turkle 1985, 2011; Richardson 2015, 2019; Seibt et al. 2016). In the end, we have to rethink the very nature of relationship (and normative expectations they entail) that we can have with machines.

Second, there is often an implicit assumption that a person is the only possible subject of respect (see e.g. Dillon, 2018). This restriction on the subject of respect is implicit in the very concept of respect, which seems to involve a bundle of various cognitive attitudes (at least, a belief about respectworthiness of someone/something) and affective attitudes (emotive states produced by such belief).³ Under this framework, robots and AI, no matter how complex, are excluded from the domain of respecting beings. The appeal of this position is understandable. At least in the current state of technological development, robots cannot feel, take a stance or have beliefs. We still can talk about “respectful” robots, and technology more broadly, in the same way as we may talk about “loving” or “caring” robots. But this will always be meant in an indirect sense, either as a metaphor, or as a statement about simulation or the imitation of human attitudes and patterns of human action.

The question I want to tackle is how we can talk about respect in its application to robots without the inverted commas. This question requires a closer look at the concept of respectfulness, and the ways in which it can be manifested. This boils down to asking: *What does it mean for a robot to be respectful?* How can we conceptualise respectfulness as an

¹ See for example Breazeal (2002).

² Excluding animal companionship.

³ For a review of various theories of respect, including the respect for persons, as well as a list of literature, I refer the reader to Dillon 2018 and Giorgini & Irrera 2017.

attribute of an animate artefact in such a way that we (a) won't lose anything substantial from the phenomenon of respect itself, but at the same time (b) acknowledge the unique ontological status of AI?

Robots are not capable of taking any stance, let alone feel respect. But this does not mean that robots cannot *be respectful*. They can be respectful but in a way that is different from the way humans can. For a robot to be respectful, it means that its algorithms and hardware are designed by the principles of respect which subsequently manifest in its activities and interaction with its users. This means re-conceptualizing respectfulness. The task is, then, to understand:

- a) To what extent are having certain cognitive capacities (such as beliefs, acknowledgements, judgements, commitments) and emotive capacities (emotions and feelings) needed for being respectful? These will have to be reserved for people responsible for the crucial stages of the process that leads to the robot's functioning in an interpersonal relationship, such as the design and development of robots (e.g. programmers and engineers), its integration into society, and its professional use (e.g. medical staff or care-providers employing a robot in their practice).
- b) Which part of being respectful can and should be played by robots, and in which way?

I will argue that robot respectfulness is a case of *mediated respectfulness* or *respectfulness by design*. By this I mean that a robot can only be attributed respectfulness in a proper sense if its interactions with persons reflect the respectful attitude of the humans involved in its design and operation. At the core of this concept lies the distinction between *behavioural and attitudinal aspects of respect*, which in the case of robot respectfulness can be spelled out as:

- a) robotic actions (or other forms of operations) that are determined by principles that
- b) reflect the corresponding standing attitude of respect by humans who are involved in its design, implementation and professional use (*stance-respect*).

Respectfulness as an attribute of robotic actions is thus not an isolated phenomenon, it cannot be taken apart from the intentions of humans involved in its design, production and professional use. At the same time, this attitude is not experienced by the user in an immediate way, as it happens in the case of a direct human-to-human interaction (human intention → human action). It is mediated through the design of the systems that determine the robotic choice of actions: human/robot-to-human interaction (human intention → robot action).

By stance-respect in this case, I understand a commitment on the side of designers, implementers and users *to apply certain well-justified principles of how to treat others based on a well-justified value assumption*. These considerations or principles could, for example, take the form of a professional code. Action-respect can then be understood as the application of these principles to the actual design, implementation and use of robots as service-providers or as players in interpersonal relationships. For a robot, this implies that it is respectful when its functions (actions, elements of design, narrative that they carry, etc.) in the interaction with humans are determined by the considerations of respect. This also implies that these respectful robotic functions reflect the commitment to such treatment by the humans involved in all stages of robots' development and integration into society. I call robot respectfulness a mediated respectfulness or respectfulness by design because it reflects and instantiates

attitudes of humans to humans, that is, the attitudes of professionals involved in robotics to the users-benefactors of robotic services. In other words, the design must acknowledge that which the robot must implement in its actions.

Respect is granted on the basis of a certain value. When it comes to the ethical justification of the principles underlying stance-respect, the question we should ask is: What value does it make sense to respect so that respect becomes *an ethical category*, i.e. that it can be applied to everyone in the same manner? I argue that the best candidate is the intrinsic value of personhood. That is, what matters is *recognizing the value of humanity and committing to treating human beings in the way that they deserve and that does not diminish their humanity*. I thus equal stance-respect with respect to persons. I define the respect to persons as a commitment to not undermine core values that make someone a person. Among these core values I will discuss intellect, rationality of emotional reactions and reactive attitudes, autonomy (when applicable), personal integrity, and trust in expertise. In the end, I will make a suggestion about the ways in which the design, implementation, and use of AI and robotics can reflect valuing these attributes of personhood.

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